

A STUDY OF CREATIVITY OF SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

Creativity is the ability to discover new solutions to problems or to produce new ideas, innovations or work of art. Creativity stands for capacity to accept challenge, freedom to exercise choice, readiness to change self and capacity to change one's environment. It is a precious source of emergence development and survival of man's culture through ages. Creativity has been perceived as a multiphase, normally distributed mental ability. It is a complex process involving a concept of self and relationship to one's environment. Academic Achievement is of paramount importance particularly in the present socio-economic and cultural contents. It forms the main basis of admission and promotion in a class. In the present education set up, the examination plays a predominant roll in assessing the talent of an individual. Intelligence refers to mental abilities. It is general mental adaptability to new problems and conditions of life. The researcher has highlighted the creativity of school going adolescents in relation to their academic achievement and intelligence in this study.

Keywords: Creativity, Adolescent, Academic Achievement and Intelligence

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Introduction

The over broadening spectrum of education and scientific development has raised the question of better learning and better achievement. Education no doubt signifies gain or accomplishment or performance carried out successfully by an individual or a group on the completion of a task whether it is academic, manual, personal or social but today, greater premium is being laid on the academic achievement. Academic being a crucial area and the main center of educational research has always been regarded as a case of educational growth as it play an important and most significant role in shaping career of individual and planning for a future education.

Creativity is also visualized as multivariate phenomenon. It is a process of becoming sensitive to problems, deficiencies, gaps of knowledge, missing elements, disharmonious

and so on, identifying the difficulties, searching for solutions, making guesses or formulating hypotheses about the deficiencies; retesting and testing hypotheses and possibly modifying and retesting them and finally communicating results. Education at different stage is geared to different aims but no one can deny the fact that the academic development or achievement of the students continues to be the main concern and the most important goal of education at all different stages. Academic achievement is one important part of the wider term educational growth, which includes growth in all aspects. It refers to the pupil's knowledge attainment and skills developed in the school subjects, such as reading, writing the subjects, which are assessed by the authorities with the help of achievement tests in the form of school examination.

Need and Importance of the study

As the recent education system provides no direction to creative domain of the child. Teachers do not recognize the creativeness in children. Therefore, if creativity is found to be a significant predictor of achievement in different subjects, then parents, teachers and educational planner will recognize the importance of intelligence and creativity while making educational programmes.

All findings vary from one another, which encourage the investigator to explore this field further. Moreover the investigator concluded that this issue still remains a current debatable issue among the research psychologists and research scholars. Therefore, the investigator decided to probe deep into relationship of creativity with intelligence and academic achievement of adolescents.

Since both intelligence and creativity represents two distinguishable mode of the same intellectual functioning, it can be said that there is a possibility of substantial overlap between two modes and the same intellectual functioning. Moreover as the research findings related to intelligence creativity and their relationship with academic achievement give us conflict results, therefore it was though proper to undertake the present study with a view to understand the role played by intelligence and academic achievement in creativity.

Related Literature

Aggarwal & Aggarwal (1999) examined creativity and intelligence: exploration with sex difference, intended to investigate the sex difference in creativity of school going children from class VI to VIII from the city of Agra. Baqer Mehdi test was used. The findings indicated that boys were more creative than girls and there was significant difference between two groups.

Gaganpreet (2004) reported that academic achievement and intelligence are positively correlated with each other. Students with high academic achievement have low academic stress and high intelligence.

Kagade (2004) worked out the various personality factors with high and low academic achievement and intelligence. He concluded that IXth and Xth class male and female students differ in academic achievement and intelligence due to parental and social influence.

Singh (2006) found that the academic achievements of students were significantly related to creativity. He found that high creative student's achievement was higher as compared to low creative students. He also concluded that originality measure of verbal creativity was significantly related with academic achievement of the students in fine arts.

Narula (2007) recognized a sample of 700 students of IX class studying in senior secondary schools of Punjab concluded significant positive correlation between the variables of creativity and academic achievement. Significant difference was also obtained between the creativity of boys and girls at 0.01 level of significance.

Dhall et al. (2009) analyzed intelligence as related to self-confidence and academic achievement of school students by taking a sample of one thousand students. They found that there was a significant relationship between academic achievement and intelligence of secondary school students; there existed a significant difference between boys and girls of secondary school in terms of intelligence; there existed significant difference between boys and girls of secondary school in terms of academic achievement.

Anees (2013) conducted a study of academic, achievement in relation to intelligence of class VII students. The present study, deals with the identification of magnitude of the relationship, between intelligence and, academic, achievement of class VIII students. The sample consisted of 180 students from high school and AMU Girls high school. The culture faire intelligent test constructed by R.B. Cattell was employed. The main finding of the study is that there is positive correlation between intelligence and academic achievement and no significant, difference between boys, and girls was found, on the measure of academic achievement.

Parveen (2014) analyzed the relationship between intelligence and academic achievement of secondary school level students. The Sample of the study consisted class tenth of 150 secondary level students (75 boys and 75 girls) from AMU Aligarh schools. Group Test of Mental Ability by R.K. Tondon was used to find out intelligence of students and for measuring academic achievement the annual examination marks of the students were

used. From The results of the study had been found that intelligence positively and significantly related with academic achievement of secondary level students.

Seng, Hanafi, Taslikhan, and Raman (2016) aimed to identify students' emotional intelligence level and to what extent emotional intelligence influences students' academic achievement. A total of 406 people form 5 students from nine schools in Limbang District, Sarawak were involved in this study.

Kaur, Harvinder, (2019), found that, there is no significant difference between male and female students in their creativity and academic achievement.

Chauhan, Suman (2019) found that there is significant difference between Boys and Girls in relation to their Academic achievement level. Boys exhibit better academic achievement compared to girls. There is significant difference between academic achievement among ADHD and normal students. It means that academic achievement of normal students is better than ADHD students.

Premendra, H. (2019) found that the scientific creativity is significantly correlated with Intelligence factor. Male students of XI grade with above average, average and below average intelligence do not differ from one another on originality factor of scientific creativity.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher has done his research on the topic "A Study of Creativity of School Going Adolescents in Relation to their Academic Achievement and Intelligence."

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the present study were as follows:

1. To study the difference between high and low creative ability on the academic achievement of school going adolescents.
2. To find out the difference between high and low creative ability on the intelligence of school going adolescents.
3. To study the difference between male and female school going adolescents on the variable creativity, academic achievement and intelligence.
4. To draw out the difference between rural and urban school going adolescents on the variable creativity, academic achievement and intelligence.
5. To study the difference between government and private schools' adolescents students on the variable creativity, academic achievement and intelligence.

Hypotheses of the study

Following hypotheses were formulated for the research:

1. There will be no significant difference between high and low creativity ability school going adolescents on their academic achievement.
2. There will be no significant difference between high and low creativity ability school going adolescents on their intelligence.
3. There will be no significant difference in creativity ability, academic achievement and intelligence of male and female school going adolescents.
4. There will be no significant difference in creativity ability, academic achievement and intelligence of rural and urban of school going adolescents.
5. There will be no significant difference between private and government schools adolescent students on their creativity ability, academic achievement and intelligence.

Selection of Sample

The research investigation was carried out on 600 male and female, rural and urban school going adolescents of Hanumangarh and Sri Ganga Nagar districts. The sample was randomly selected from the government and private schools affiliated to Rajasthan School Education Board.

Delimitation of the study

1. The present study was delimited to 600 adolescent students of XI the class.
2. This study was delimited to two districts (Hanumangarh and Shri Ganga Nagar) of Rajasthan state.

Methodology & Research design

This study method was simple normative type survey. In the investigation, creativity was dependent variables where as intelligence and academic achievement were independent variables. And also found out the difference between male /female, rural/urban and government / private school's adolescent students on the variable creativity ability, academic achievement and intelligence.

Statistical techniques Used

The researcher has used Mean, standard deviation and t-test as statistical techniques for analyzing and manipulating the data.

Tools Used

The following tools were used in the study:-

- Non verbal test of creativity thinking by- Baquer Mehdi (1985)

- Group Test of General Mental Ability Test by Dr. S. Jalota
- Academic score of class 10th from school record.

Main findings of the study

1. There is no significant difference between high and low group of creative ability school going adolescents in their academic achievement.
2. There is a significant difference between high and low group of creative ability school going adolescents in their intelligence. Those students have high creative ability are more intelligent than the low creative group.
3. There is no significant difference between male and female students in their creative ability.
4. There is a significant difference between rural and urban students in their creative ability. Rural adolescents have high creative ability than the urban.
5. There is a significant difference between male and female students in their academic achievement. Female students are higher academic achievement than the male students.
6. There is a significant difference between rural and urban students' academic achievement. Urban students have higher academic achievement than the rural students.
7. There is no significant difference between male and female students in their intelligence.
8. There is no significant difference between rural and urban students in their intelligence.
9. There is no significant difference between government school and private school students in their creative ability.
10. There is a significant difference between government school and private school students in their academic achievement. Students of private school have high academic achievement than the government school students.
11. There is no significant difference between government school and private school students in their intelligence.

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